

Fuzzy Optimization in Metabolic Systems

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Abstract—The optimization of biological systems, which is a branch of metabolic engineering, has generated a lot of industrial and academic interest for a long time. In the last decade, metabolic engineering approaches based on mathematical optimizations have been used extensively for the analysis and manipulation of metabolic networks. In practical optimization of metabolic reaction networks, designers have to manage the nature of uncertainty resulting from qualitative characters of metabolic reactions, e.g., the possibility of enzyme effects. A deterministic approach does not give an adequate representation for metabolic reaction networks with uncertain characters. Fuzzy optimization formulations can be applied to cope with this problem. A fuzzy multi-objective optimization problem can be introduced for finding the optimal engineering interventions on metabolic network systems considering the resilience phenomenon and cell viability constraints. The accuracy of optimization results depends heavily on the development of essential kinetic models of metabolic networks. Kinetic models can quantitatively capture the experimentally observed regulation data of metabolic systems and are often used to find the optimal manipulation of external inputs. To address the issues of optimizing the regulatory structure of metabolic networks, it is necessary to consider qualitative effects, e.g., the resilience phenomena and cell viability constraints. Combining the qualitative and quantitative descriptions for metabolic networks makes it possible to design a viable strain and accurately predict the maximum possible flux rates of desired products. Considering the resilience phenomena in metabolic networks can improve the predictions of gene intervention and maximum synthesis rates in metabolic engineering. Two case studies will present in the conference to illustrate the phenomena.

Keywords—Fuzzy multi-objective optimization problem, kinetic model, metabolic engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

OPTIMIZATION is the process of making something as good or effective as possible. This definition is similar to optimization in a fuzzy environment. More generally, it means finding “best available” values of some objective function given a defined domain, including a variety of different types of objective functions and domains [1]. Regarding to optimization in biology, we should mention Darwin’s evolutionary theory that living organisms have evolved to maximize their chances for survival. The use of optimization has allowed biologists not only to describe patterns or mechanisms but to predict, from first principles, how organisms should be designed [2]. Many articles have been applying optimization methods for solving

biological problems. Model-based optimization problems can be classified as stoichiometric and kinetic models. Stoichiometric models can be obtained through the reaction topology of a network. Stoichiometric models do not require kinetic data and are easy to construct. However, they have shortages of handling regulatory dynamics in a metabolic network. Kinetic models, e.g., generalized mass action (GMA) and Michaelis-Menten formulations are generally formulated as nonlinear equations with more information to describe system characteristics [3]. Indirect optimization methods (IOMs) convert a nonlinear kinetic model into an S-system model [4]. The model becomes a linear system so that the problem can be solved by a linear programming method efficiently.

Optimization problems for metabolic networks can be categorized as single-objective and multi-objective formulations, depending on the design purpose. Most studies on microbial metabolic engineering focus on only a single objective, i.e., maximize the synthesis rate of a desired metabolite. In contrast, a multi-objective optimization approach attempts to find the solutions that are optimal for many objectives simultaneously. However, most approaches are considered optimization in a crisp environment. In general, some biological optimization problems imply finding the best compromise among several conflicting demands in a fuzzy situation. For example, experimental results show that a micro-organism may reflect resilience phenomenon after stressful environmental changes and genetic modification. The resilience phenomenon indicates that a mutant strain tries to recover to its original “wild-type” characteristics. MOMA [5] and ROOM [6] were applied to handle this phenomenon. An optimal design may be over-predicted if we do not consider resilience effects. In this article, a generalized fuzzy multi-objective optimization is introduced to handle resilience effects. We introduce fuzzy programming approaches to determine optimal design for biological systems in a fuzzy environment and then apply to two metabolic network systems for illustrating the approach.

II. METHODS

An optimization problem in a crisp environment can be expressed as follows:

Crisp objective function:

$$\max_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

Crisp inequality constraints:

$$g_j(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0, j = 1, \dots, p$$

The crisp optimization problem is to find decision variables

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\mathbf{x} such that the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ should be maximized and fulfilled the constraints $g_j(\mathbf{x})$ completely. Suppose that the vector \mathbf{x}^* in the green area (feasible domain) of Fig. 1 is the maximum point of the crisp optimization problem. According to optimality, the point \mathbf{x}^* is said to be a locally maximum solution, if no point in the neighborhood has a function value greater than $f(\mathbf{x}^*)$. Considering that a point \mathbf{x}^1 located nearby the maximum point \mathbf{x}^* , $f(\mathbf{x}^1) > f(\mathbf{x}^*)$, and one of inequality constraints is greater than zero at the point \mathbf{x}^1 , i.e., $g_j(\mathbf{x}^1) > 0$, is not an optimal solution, because it is outside the crisp feasible domain defined sharply.

Fig. 1 The feasible domain for a crisp optimization problem

In general, an objective and/or constraints for a biological optimization problem are not sharply defined and flexible. A fuzzy formulation can be applied to describe such flexible situations. The fuzzy optimization problem is expressed as follows:

Fuzzy objective function:

$$\text{Fuzzy max}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n} f(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

Fuzzy inequality constraints:

$$g_j(\mathbf{x}) \leq [0, \varepsilon_j], j = 1, \dots, p$$

The fuzzy optimization problem is to find decision variables \mathbf{x} such that the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ should be maximized as well as possible and the constraints $g_j(\mathbf{x})$ should be possibly well satisfied, respectively. The definition is literally different to the crisp optimization. Fig. 2 shows the feasible domain for fuzzy and crisp optimization problems. In general, the crisp feasible domain is a subset of the fuzzy domain. Both points \mathbf{x}^* and \mathbf{x}^1 on the fuzzy feasible domain are the candidate solutions to the fuzzy optimization problem. Suppose that $f(\mathbf{x}^1) > f(\mathbf{x}^*)$, but the inequalities $g_j(\mathbf{x}^1) = \varepsilon_j > 0$ are less satisfactory than those of \mathbf{x}^* . As a result, a trade-off procedure has to be carried out to obtain a compromise solution for the fuzzy optimization problem. A fuzzy solution, then, may be viewed as an intersection of the given goal and constraints. A satisfactory solution may be obtained by assigning various values of ε_j (a

brute force method), and then solve each problem to obtain the corresponding solution, which is referred to as a candidate solution. The satisfactory solution is then picked up from the candidate solutions. In general, the brute force method is inefficient.

Fig. 2 Description of the crisp and fuzzy feasible domains

We can elicit membership functions to fuzzy objective and constraints in order to solve fuzzy optimization problems. We first define a membership function for each constraint and objective as shown in Fig. 3. The membership function for each fuzzy constraint is a strictly monotonically decreasing function for evaluating the degree of satisfaction. The membership function value or satisfactory grade is equal to one if the corresponding constraint is less than its lower bound g_j^{LB} . In contrast, the satisfactory grade is equal to zero if the constraint is greater than its upper bound. The constraint is somewhat acceptable if its level lies between the lower and upper bounds. Similarly, the membership function for objective is defined as a strictly monotone increasing function as shown in the blue curve. The satisfactory grade is zero if the objective is less than its lower bound and one if the objective is greater than its upper bound. By defining each fuzzy objective and fuzzy constraint, the fuzzy optimization problem is then transferred to the maximizing decision problem that is to find maximum intersection of the objective and constraints.

Fig. 3 Description of membership function for objective and inequality constraint

IV. CONCLUSION

The optimization of biological systems, which is a branch of metabolic engineering, has generated a lot of industrial and academic interest for a long time. The ultimate goal of this optimization is to find the optimal mutation strategy for improving productivity and to detect new target enzymes for curing metabolic diseases. This study introduces a generalized fuzzy multi-objective optimization approach to find optimal design for metabolic network systems.

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to represent the low dose objective. Three decision making criteria were combined with the optimal design problem for detecting target enzymes. As a result, the drug design problem was formulated as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem. The commercial software, GAMS with BONMIN and KNITRO solvers, were applied to identify target enzymes for curing hyperuricemia caused by PRPPS overactivity and HGPRT deficiency, respectively. In this study, we introduced a nested hybrid differential evolution [10] to solve the MINLP problem including the pathological state caused by PRPPS overactivity and HGPRT deficiency, simultaneously. Fig. 7 shows the overall satisfactory grades with and without prescribed diet control. The detailed computational procedures will discuss in the conference. From Fig. 7, we observe that only one enzyme is unable to achieve the goal for remedying hyperuricemia, which is caused by overactivity of the enzyme PRPPS and HGPRT deficiency. For the case of no prescription diet control, one three-enzyme target {gnuc, ada, den} has the overall satisfactory grade of about 16%. Moreover, if we consider the prescription diet control of R5P and Pi, the overall satisfactory grade can achieve to 54%.

Fig. 7 The overall satisfactory grades for the treatment of disease caused by PRPPS hyperactivity and HGPRT deficiency, simultaneously